

ACTIVE CONTROL OF CRACK-TIP STRESS INTENSITY BY CONTRACTION OF SHAPE MEMORY TiNi FIBERS EMBEDDED IN EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITE: DEPENDENCY OF STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR ON CRACK-TIP DOMAIN SIZE

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SUMMARY: Shape memory TiNi fiber reinforced/epoxy matrix composite is fabricated to demonstrate the suppression effect of crack-tip stress concentration and the increase of fracture toughness (K value) of the composite. The increase of fracture toughness is attributed to the compressive stress field in the matrix which is induced when the prestrained TiNi fibers contract to the initial length upon heating above austenitic finish temperature of TiNi fiber ($T > A_f$). The dependence of K value on the prestrain value of TiNi fibers as well as the compressive stress domain size between a crack-tip and fiber are discussed based on the analytical equivalent inclusion model for a composite. The experimental data agreed well to theoretical predictions.

KEYWORDS: shape memory alloy, smart composite, stress intensity factor, photoelasticity, phase transformation, fracture toughness, crack closure

INTRODUCTION

Enhancement of the mechanical strength (stiffness, yield strength and fracture toughness) and suppression of the degradation damage (crack, delamination) during in service time are very important subjects in the development of engineering composite systems. Recently, the authors developed a new type of "smart" composite where shape memory TiNi fiber was used as a reinforcement and actuator to improve the mechanical properties of the composite at higher use temperatures above the inverse transformation temperature ($T > f$) of TiNi alloy [1,2,3,4] up to the present, the enhancing effects of the tensile yield strength, the suppression effect of fatigue crack propagation in TiNi fiber reinforced Al matrix composite (TiNi/Al) [5] and the increase of the fracture toughness (K-value) in a TiNi/epoxy composite have been experimentally confirmed because of the large compressive stresses in the matrix by the shape memory shrinkages of embedded fibers.

In the present paper, shape memory TiNi fiber reinforced/epoxy matrix composites are fabricated to re-verify the active damage control for cracks in the composite by using

experimental photoelasticity method. The suppression effect of crack-tip stress concentration and the increase of fracture toughness (K) are investigated. Especially, the dependencies of K value on not only the prestrains of TiNi fibers but also the compressive stress domain size between a crack-tip and the embedded fibers are discussed based on the analytical equivalent inclusion model for a composite.

DESIGN CONCEPT FOR SHAPE MEMORY COMPOSITE

Thermoelastic shape memory effect (i.e. shape memory and recovery phenomenon) takes place during martensite (M) to austenite (A) phase transformation in SMA with increasing temperature. Therefore, material functional properties of SMA changes clearly depending on the changes of temperature as summarized in Fig. 1. It should be noticed as a unique property that SMA shows more higher stiffness (2-3 times) and large recovery stress at the higher temperature region due to inversely thermoelastic phase transformation in opposition to weakening of those properties in the general metals.

In consequence, SMA natively has the smart functions, i.e., (1)sensor (thermal), (2)actuator (shape memory deformation) and (3) memory and shape recovery (namely, processor function). These unique properties natively with SMA can be utilized to strengthen the composite.

The design concept of enhancing the mechanical properties of the SMA composite is schematically shown in Fig.2. TiNi fibers are heat-treated to shape-memorize their initial length at higher temperatures ($>T_f$), then quenched to room temperature (nearly, martensite start temperature $=M_s$), given tensile prestrain $\epsilon_T (>0)$ and embedded in the matrix material to form a composite. The composite is then heated to temperature ($>A_f$) at which the TiNi fibers tend to shrink back to their initial length by the amount of prestrain ϵ_T , then the matrix is subjected to compressive stress. It is this compressive stress in the matrix that contributes to the enhancement of the tensile properties of the composite and fracture toughness.

EXPERIMENT

Experimental processing, mechanical testing of TiNi/epoxy composite is described. The shape memorized TiNi fibers (Ti-50.2at%Ni) of 400 μm diameter supplied by Kantoc Ltd., Fujisawa, Japan were arranged in a mold to which photoelastic epoxy and specified amount of hardener were poured and then kept at 130°C for 2 hours for curing. After curing, as-molded composite was cooled to room temperature. During the process, TiNi fibers were kept in tension with four different prestrains of 0, 1, 3 and 5%. A side notch which has three different lengths 3, 4, 4.8 mm were then cut into the as molded composite specimen for changing the domain size (D) between a crack-tip and a fiber. The geometry of the composite specimen is shown in Fig.3. In order to determine the transformation temperatures and stress-strain relations of TiNi fiber, tensile test of TiNi fiber at different temperatures (T) was conducted. The stress vs. strain curves at constant temperature: T=20, 40, 60, 80 and 100°C were obtained as shown in Fig.4. From another relationship between strain vs. T at constant stress of 94 MPa, four transformation temperatures of TiNi fiber were determined: Martensitic start $M_s=31^\circ\text{C}$, Martensite finish $M_f=1^\circ\text{C}$, Austenitic start $A_s=57^\circ\text{C}$, and Austenitic finish $A_f=63^\circ\text{C}$. A constant load of 392 N was applied to TiNi/epoxy specimen by the controlled tensile test machine to form the third or fourth photoelastic fringe pattern. The changes of

number of fringe pattern lines developed around the notch tip were measured at different constant temperatures of 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100°C.

Fig.1: Material properties of shape memory alloy with increasing temperature

Fig.2: Design concept of SMA smart composite

Fig.3: Geometry of TiNi/epoxy composite specimen with a side notch.

Fig.4: Stress-strain curves of TiNi fiber at different temperatures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dependence of Stress Intensity Factor (K-value) on the Prestrain Value(e)

The results of the photoelasticity experiment are shown in Fig.5. Fig.5.(a),(b),(c) and (d) denote the fringe pattern developed around the notch tip in the composite with prestrain 0,1,3 and 5% tested at 80°C, respectively. Fig.5 demonstrates clearly the shape memory effect as the stress intensity factor measured at 80°C above Af, respectively. From the Fig.5, shape memory effect of the embedded TiNi fibers reduce the stress concentration with increasing prestrain value. Stress intensity factor KI can be computed from

$$K_I = \frac{n\sqrt{2}\pi r_m}{\alpha t \sin\theta_m} \left[1 + \left(\frac{2}{3 \tan\theta_m} \right)^2 \right]^{-0.5} \left[1 + \frac{2 \tan(3\theta_m/2)}{3 \tan\theta_m} \right] \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of the fringe, t is the composite plate thickness, α is the epoxy photo-elasticity sensitivity constant, r and θ_m are, respectively, the distance and angle in polar coordinates at point M, shown schematically in Fig.6. The experimental results of the reductions in the stress intensity factor KI are plotted in Fig.7 as a function of temperature along X-axis under three different prestrains in a case of notch length of 4.8mm. The value of KI ratio in Y axis means the normalized value of KI which can be calculated from dividing absolute KI value in a certain prestrained specimen by the KI value of zero-prestrained specimen. KI ratio clearly decreases with increasing temperature above 60°C which is nearly equal to Af temperature of TiNi fiber. It indicates that the shape memory shrinkages of TiNi fibers above 60°C can suppress the stress intensity at a crack-tip. Fig.8 shows the relationship between KI-value ratio and prestrain value in three cases of notch lengths. Stress intensity decreases with increasing prestrain value where the decrease of KI experimentally seems most intense in the most small domain size at a=4.8mm.

Fig.5 Photoelastic fringe patterns around a side notch of TiNi/epoxy specimen loaded by 392N at 80 °C with different prestrains: (a) 0%, (b) 1%, (c) 3% and (d) 5%

Fig.6 Photoelastic fringe pattern schematically developed in front of a crack size a .

Fig.7 Stress intensity factor K_I -ratio as a functions of temperature under three different prestrains in a case of crack length of 4.8mm.

Fig.8 Stress intensity factor K_I -value ratio vs. prestrain in three different cases of crack lengths.

Dependence of Stress Intensity Factor (K-value) on the Domain Size (D)

Lastly, the reduction in stress intensity factor due to prestrain and shape memory effect is estimated by the analytical modeling which generally consists of the steps: (1) computation of the compressive residual stress in the matrix, (2) prediction of crack-tip stress intensity factor change ΔK_I . Following Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method [5,6,7] by using eigen strain concept as well as the equilibrium equation of force between TiNi fiber stress and average matrix stress in axisymmetry along the axis of fiber direction, average stress change of the matrix (q) can be calculated. When a crack tip is subjected to compressive stress q, then, the stress intensity factor K_I is given by following equation [8].

$$\Delta K_I = 2q \sqrt{\frac{2D}{\pi}} \quad (2)$$

where D is the length of the compressive stress domain between a crack-tip and the embedded fiber. Eqn(2) was originally formulated by Tada et al. has been used by several researchers [9,10]. The values of D in the present experiment are 2,1 and 0.2 mm respectively for three notch depths as shown in Fig.3. The value of q is in unit of MPa, and computed from the residual stress model for matrix.

As a result, the predicted values of K_I are plotted as solid points in Fig.9. As to the relationship between K_I ratio and prestrain, the analytical model explains the same trend as the experimental results, i.e., K_I -value decreases with increase in prestrain, however, the predictions are apt to show larger values than those of the experiment.

Fig.9 Relationship between K_I change and prestrain in experimental data and FEM analysis.

CONCLUSION

Shape memory TiNi fiber reinforced /epoxy matrix composite was fabricated to demonstrate the suppression effect of crack-tip stress concentration and the increase of fracture toughness (K value) of the composite. The increase of fracture toughness was attributed to the compressive stress field in the matrix which was induced when the prestrained TiNi fibers contract to the initial length upon heating above austenitic finish temperature of TiNi fiber ($T > A_f$). As to the dependence of K values on the prestrain value of TiNi fibers and the compressive stress domain size between a crack-tip and fiber, the analytical model explains the same trend as the experimental results.

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